

EHSVEC CURRICULAR PHILOSOPHY

“The Philosophy of Purpose and Fulfillment in Life”

INTRODUCTION

At the core of the EHSVEC curriculum philosophy is a fundamental truth: everything created has a purpose. This truth is evident in our experiences, and even those who do not recognize God or believe the Bible can observe this in the smallest details of our lives.

PURSUING HAPPINESS

Pursuit of Happiness Enshrined in Our Constitution

When the founders of the United States declared independence from Great Britain, they asserted, “We hold these truths to be self-evident, that all men are created equal, that they are endowed by their Creator with certain unalienable Rights, that among these are Life, Liberty, and the pursuit of Happiness” (Declaration of Independence, 1776). This highlights that one of God's gifts is the freedom to determine what makes us happy or fulfilled. Although the Philippine Constitution does not use this exact phrase, it contains provisions that assert this right.

The Preamble of the Philippine Constitution expresses the aspiration to “build a just and humane society” and to promote the common good. Additionally, Article II, Section 5 mandates the government to maintain peace and order, protect life, liberty, and property, and promote the general welfare.

Furthermore, the Bill of Rights in Article III, which limits the state's power, guarantees fundamental rights such as due process and freedom of abode.

The State Can Only Provide the Right Environment; It Cannot Provide Answer to Life's Meaning

While the Constitution grants the state the power to protect individuals' right to pursue happiness, it cannot answer why we are here or what will give us fulfillment. This limitation exists not only because providing such answers would violate our freedom but also because the state recognizes that the individual can only answer this question.

Finding Happiness Early

A person's sense of fulfillment remains insatiable until it is truly satisfied. The pursuit of happiness continues until we genuinely find it. While it may seem like there is no deadline except death, the Bible advises that we should know the answer to our purpose and fulfillment while we are young. Our time on earth is limited, and there is much to enjoy if we already know what truly makes us happy. It is unwise to spend our limited days on earth in trial and error. Solomon advises the young, “Remember your Creator in the days of your youth...” (Ecclesiastes 12:1). That is why we ought it to the children to teach these truths to them as young as they are.

Losing One's Soul Can Be One's Greatest Regret

At the heart of our pursuit of happiness is the question of our purpose and fulfillment in life. Happiness lies in the answer to this question. Whether or not one believes in God or accepts the Bible as His word, and whether or not one realizes that their entire being is seeking the answer to this question, our thoughts, words, and actions reflect the truth that we are merely

strangers in this world and cannot find our fulfillment here.

Jesus Himself said that gaining the whole world means nothing if we lose our soul (Mark 8:36). When God created man, He breathed into him the breath of life, and man became a living soul (Genesis 2:7).

Man's soul is his life and wasting it in pursuit of the wrong things will be his greatest regret. To lose one's soul means death, not of the physical body but spiritual death, which means eternal separation from the Creator. A person is not truly alive if he is not connected to the Source of life.

Where the Answer Can Be Found

The loss of one's soul also means losing life's purpose and fulfillment. Without God, mankind remains "in between, in the misty flats, drifting to and fro" (Oxenham, n.d.). Our purpose and fulfillment can only be found in our Creator, who intends for every man to come to Him for the answer to the question of purpose and fulfillment. He encourages us to do so and His promise is that we will surely find Him (Jeremiah 29:13), in finding Him, we discover our purpose.

The Bible says that God has placed eternity in our hearts (Ecclesiastes 3:11). Eternity refers to things that are not temporal or material, things that do not age, perish, or disappear in time, but remain forever.

This world is temporary, including power, fame, influence, and money. God compares the temporariness of our world to grass and flowers (Isaiah 40:8). Even our own existence is compared to dew or fog, which disappears with the sunrise (James 4:14). These things are not evil in themselves; God bestows them to be enjoyed and used for His purpose. But man should not depend on them or think that accumulating them is the purpose of life.

We cannot be satisfied by anything temporary because our Creator designed us for eternity. Augustine expressed this when he said, "You have made us for

Thyself, and our hearts are restless until they find their rest in Thee" (Augustine, 1997). Blaise Pascal said, "At the heart of every man there is a void that can only be filled by God" (Pascal, 1670/1995). This statement reflects Pascal's views on the human condition and his belief in the inherent emptiness within individuals, which he argues can only be truly fulfilled through a connection with the divine.

The Ultimate Fulfillment: Glorifying God and Enjoying Him Forever

To live a life that pleases God is to understand our place within His greater design. The ultimate fulfillment does not come from accumulating wealth, achieving fame, or amassing personal accolades, but from realizing our role in His grand narrative. Our purpose is not defined by temporary accomplishments but by an eternal truth: our lives were created to glorify God and to find our joy in Him forever.

As the Westminster Shorter Catechism profoundly states, "Man's chief end is to glorify God and to enjoy Him forever" (Westminster Shorter Catechism, 1647). This guiding principle directs us toward a life where we find contentment, meaning, and purpose in our relationship with God. It calls us to align our goals, values, and actions with His will, recognizing that our true fulfillment lies in this relationship.

APPLICATION

Integrating Purpose into the Curriculum

At EHSVEC, our curriculum philosophy is rooted in this foundational truth: true fulfillment comes from knowing and enjoying God. This understanding drives our approach to education, encouraging students to see their academic, personal, and spiritual development as interconnected.

Our curriculum is not just about academic excellence; it aims to nurture a holistic understanding of life, teaching students to recognize that their purpose extends

beyond their immediate goals and achievements. By fostering an environment that promotes spiritual, intellectual, and emotional growth, we guide students toward a life of fulfillment, grounded in the eternal truths of God's Word.

Educating for Purpose and Fulfillment

The aim of education is not merely to impart knowledge but to shape individuals who will contribute meaningfully to society, grounded in a purpose that transcends the material. Students must understand that their academic endeavors are part of a larger calling — to live in alignment with God's plan. This involves cultivating virtues like integrity, compassion, responsibility, and faith, while also encouraging them to explore and understand their unique role in God's creation.

The Bible encourages us to "do all to the glory of God" (1 Corinthians 10:31). This principle should permeate every area of life, including education. Students should not only strive for academic excellence but also seek to serve God and others through their studies and actions. Education, therefore, becomes a means of fulfilling the divine calling, shaping individuals who are equipped not only with knowledge but with wisdom, character, and purpose.

The Role of Educators in Shaping Purpose-Driven Lives

Educators at EHSVEC are not just teachers but mentors and guides, helping students navigate the journey of discovering their purpose. They are called to model lives that reflect a deep understanding of God's truth and to inspire students to seek fulfillment in Him.

Teachers must lead by example, demonstrating how their own education and professional endeavors align with the greater purpose of glorifying God and serving humanity.

Moreover, educators should foster an environment where students feel encouraged to ask the big questions of life: What is my purpose? Why am I here? How can I make a difference in the world? By providing students with the tools to explore these questions in a safe, supportive environment, educators equip them to develop a strong sense of purpose, helping them navigate the challenges and uncertainties of life.

The EHSVEC Vision for Future Generations

The vision of EHSVEC extends beyond the walls of the classroom. We seek to raise a generation of individuals who are not only academically prepared but also spiritually grounded and purpose-driven. By nurturing students' intellectual curiosity, emotional maturity, and spiritual depth, we prepare them to make a meaningful impact in their communities and in the world at large.

Our goal is for every student to leave EHSVEC equipped with the knowledge, wisdom, and character necessary to live a fulfilling life. This is not merely a life of success by worldly standards but a life that seeks to fulfill the higher calling given by God. In this way, education becomes a transformative journey, leading individuals to discover their true purpose, find lasting fulfillment, and ultimately live a life that glorifies God.

EHSVEC CURRICULAR PHILOSOPHY and How it Relates to DepEd Core Values

The core values of the Department of Education (DepEd) are four pillars that are needed in building good character. These, are, namely, "*Maka-Diyos, Maka-tao, Makakalikasan, at Makabansa*" (Department of Education, 2024).

The First Core Value is the Basis for the Other Three

The first of these pillars is *Maka-Diyos* (God-fearing). Observed in how a person exhibits faith in God and their love for Him, this pillar should be our basis and motivation for the other three. For example, a God-fearing person would be careful not to hurt anyone. He will be *makatao* (pro-people). They will be guided by Jesus' command to love others as we love ourselves (Matthew 22:37-40).

In addition, because the Bible says that one of the responsibilities given by God to man is to be a good steward of the planet, a God-fearing person will take care of his environment. This is what the third core value, *Makakalikasan* (Pro-environment) means.

Lastly, *Makabansa* (Patriotic), is crucial in maintaining peace and order as it refers to how a person upholds and respects the law. But we obey the laws of the land not only because we fear penalty or imprisonment, but because one of God's commands to us is to submit to the authority of government because it is God who put them in their position (Romans 13:1-5).

The Core Values and the Children Today

DepEd emphasizes the importance of integrating Core Values into their curriculum, ensuring they serve as the guiding principles for everyone within their community.

Understanding the rationale behind this decision requires recognizing the significant changes in student behavior over the past twenty years.

Today's learners exhibit a higher incidence of misbehavior and engage in a broader spectrum of violations compared to those from two decades ago.

Changes in Student Behavior Over Time

There had been an observable increase in reported misbehavior, and the top in the list is bullying. A 2015 study by Plan International found that 65% of children in the Philippines had experienced some form of bullying. The Department of Education reported that bullying cases increased by over 20% between 2014 and 2016.

Moreover, according to the 2018 Annual Report of DepEd, there has been a noticeable increase in incidents of student misbehavior, including absenteeism, disrespect towards teachers, and involvement in physical altercations.

The impact of technology on children is also raising the alarm. For example, the Child Rights Network Philippines reported in 2019 that approximately 40% of Filipino children had experienced cyberbullying.

The rapid increase in social media use has exacerbated this issue.

In addition, a study by the University of the Philippines in 2017 found that excessive screen time among Filipino youth is linked to attention problems and lower academic performance.

The mental health of children and youth today is also a concern. The National Center for Mental Health (NCMH) in the Philippines has seen a significant increase in the number of young people seeking help for anxiety and depression, with a 30% increase in calls to their crisis hotline in 2019.

The Philippine Psychiatric Association also notes a rising trend in the diagnosis of ADHD and other behavioral disorders among school-aged children.

Misbehavior Results from Man's Pursuit of Happiness

Based on our curricular philosophy, the misbehavior of the children today results from man's pursuit of happiness. To prove this point, we can look at many angles and consider many perspectives. However, there is one factor that cannot be overlooked, the family, and more than anything else, the domestic situation of a child affects them for the better or worse.

Many children enrolled in our public schools are victims of poverty or grow up in dysfunctional homes because of poverty.

According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), about 15-20% of children live in single-parent households due to separation, annulment, or abandonment.

The Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) reported that there are many children living with extended family members due to parents working abroad, commonly referred to as "left-behind children."

Moreover, a study by the Scalabrini Migration Center found that approximately

9 million Filipino children are left behind by one or both parents working abroad. This separation often results in various emotional and behavioral challenges for these children, which can be characteristic of a dysfunctional home environment.

The Council for the Welfare of Children (CWC) reported that a significant number of children experience domestic violence. According to the National Baseline Study on Violence Against Children (NBS-VAC) conducted in 2015, around 3 in 5 children experienced physical violence, and about 4 in 5 children experienced some form of psychological violence.

The DSWD also handles thousands of cases of child abuse, neglect, and exploitation annually. In 2019, the DSWD reported over 8,000 cases of child abuse, which includes physical abuse, sexual abuse, and neglect, pointing to a considerable number of children living in dysfunctional and unsafe environments.

Looking at these shocking statistics, one cannot help but see human restlessness due to our insatiable desires. Fathers leaving their wife and children to be with another woman, and mothers also do the same, are because they realized while already in a committed relationship, that it is not what will make them happy.

Because of lack of opportunity in our country, parents leave their children to their relatives to work abroad. Although this is not to say they go abroad because they are materialistic, these OFWs are one way or another influenced by how the world determines and labels someone as successful. There is nothing romantic about poverty, and the poor should be encouraged and given opportunities to and help to break the cycle of poverty, the pressure to go abroad for a quicker way to improve their lives somehow had become an illusion, so much so that one becomes willing to leave their spouse and children, risking their relationship with them exchange for promises of greener pasture, a promise no one can be sure would be fulfilled.

This situation is one of the major reasons why domestic violence and abuse, including sexual abuse of minors committed by a family member, are also on the rise. No wonder many children misbehave at school. They carry too heavy a burden in their already restless hearts.

This is the biggest challenge DepEd has to face, and it takes on that challenge by means of developing a curriculum that would emphasize the department's core values, with emphasis on the first.

To be *maka-Diyos* or God-fearing is commended in the Bible by giving a negative example of those who do not believe that He exists. They are fools (Psalm 14:1), therefore, those who believe Him are wise

When Does Change Begin

The philosophy of purpose and fulfillment in life that underpins the EHSVEC curriculum is more than an academic framework; it is a life philosophy that encourages students to find their true purpose in God.

We believe that this purpose is foundational to living a fulfilled life and that education, when grounded in this truth, is the key to unlocking that fulfillment. By guiding students toward a deeper understanding of their purpose, we hope to foster individuals who are not only knowledgeable but also wise, compassionate, and driven by a desire to honor God in all that they do.

But when do we begin to desire to honor God? EHSVEC curricular philosophy adheres to one of the most basic truths in the Bible. It is not only that man is a sinner (Romans 3:23), he also cannot save himself (Titus 3:5), and left alone, he will not even desire to be saved (Romans 3:10).

Man wants purpose and fulfillment, and we cannot find these except in God. While God has planted eternity in our hearts, or we have been programmed by our Creator

to not be satisfied by worldly and temporal things, unless God intervenes, man will continue running after persons, things, even experiences, that he thinks might give him satisfaction. However, these will only fail him.

The disappointment, dissatisfaction, and frustrations with the things that are temporal – things we spent our time, money and energy to acquire – but we realized cannot give us the sense of purpose and fulfillment we long for, should lead us to God. But then again, spiritually dead (Ephesians 2:1), there is no way man can get out of this cycle unless God gives him the desire to be free (Ephesians 2:8), and the faith that will give him that freedom. What man needs is the one that only God can give, the Gospel.

The Gospel in the Curriculum

Referred to by Paul as the power of God to save man (Romans 1:16), the Gospel is not a philosophical statement or a scientific theory, not even just a static message; it is alive because the Gospel is a person, the Gospel is Jesus Christ Himself, whom we must believe to be redeemed from the penalty and power of sin (John 3:16). That is why when asked what a person must do to be saved, Paul replied, "Believe on the Lord Jesus Christ and you will be saved..." (Acts 16:31). Therefore, the Gospel is central in our curriculum. Our curricular philosophy of purpose and fulfillment hinges on the promise of Christ to give those who believe and follow Him an abundant life (John 10:10), a life of purpose and fulfillment because it is a life that seeks to know God and to please Him. Change begins as soon as the Gospel is believed.

EHSVEC Curricular Philosophy Concept Diagram

If we are to draw the concept diagram of our philosophy, it would be like this.

It all begins with God and His love, which He bestows upon us. He created humanity to be in a close relationship with Him, desiring for us to know Him deeply and intimately. This is what it means to be one with God (1 Corinthians 6:17) or to be in Christ as Christ is in God (John 14:20), a statement so profound it cannot be completely fathomed, but the Bible provides illustrations to help us understand by faith.

Marriage between a man and a woman is the closest reflection of oneness with God. This union, as described in Genesis 2:24, Matthew 19:5, Mark 10:8, and Ephesians 5:31, signifies the sacred joining of two individuals into one flesh. From the very beginning, marriage was an institution blessed by God. Moreover, it serves as a profound metaphor for the intimate relationship God desires with us. Just as each believer is a part of the body of Christ, with Christ as the head (1 Corinthians 12:21; Colossians 1:18), the church is depicted as the Bride of Christ, with Christ as the Groom (Revelation 19:7-9). The intimacy of being part of one body is profound, yet the consummation of marriage between bride and groom represents an even deeper level of closeness.

However, God is holy, and humanity is sinful, yet through Christ's redemptive act—His death for our sins (1 Corinthians 15:3-4)—a relationship with God becomes possible. When a person believes in

Christ, they are saved and begin a transformative journey of faith. This relationship deepens as they grow in the knowledge of Christ (2 Peter 3:18), experiencing a life of purpose, fulfillment, and alignment with God's will.

The arrows indicate that everything begins and ends with God. This is why one of Jesus' titles is Alpha and Omega, the Beginning and the End (Revelation 22:13). God initiates our salvation, motivated by His love (John 3:16). Although we are sinners deserving of punishment under God's wrath, His love, demonstrated on the cross (Romans 5:8), offers salvation and reconciliation to those who believe in Christ. This is due to Christ's substitutionary death, where our sins became His, and His righteousness became ours (2 Corinthians 5:21). This righteousness, given to us the moment we believe, begins its transformative work. As new creations (2 Corinthians 5:17), the Holy Spirit instills new desires in us, especially the desire to know God more and to live according to His will, motivated by love rather than fear (John 14:15, 21). God's love compels us to love Him, characterizing the abundant life Jesus promised.

The DepEd Core Values—Maka-Diyos, Makatao, Makakalikasan, and Makabansa—can only genuinely manifest in a person who knows God's purpose for them. All this is a by-product of our relationship with God. The Bible tells us that this relationship should result in becoming like Christ, having His mindset (Philippians 2:5). This is why the cross is central to the Core Values depicted in the diagram. We should love God and our fellowmen, take care of our environment, and obey the laws of the land as Jesus would. He is our model, and God the Father is shaping us according to the likeness of His Son.

How is EHSVEC Aligned to GMRC / ESP Curriculum

The MATATAG Curriculum focuses on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs). In our EHSVEC Curriculum, we

have arranged these competencies under DepEd's Core Values, with 4-6 competencies in each grading period. Our lessons have been designed to supplement GMRC / ESP / Values Education lessons.

The Person and Work of Jesus is the theme of the curriculum, making Him our model.

The table below shows how the competencies determined by DepEd to be the most essential are arranged.

Lev	Unang Markahan 6-10 WEEKS			Ikalawang Markahan 6-10 weeks			Ikatlong Markahan 6-10 weeks		Ikaapat Markahan 6-10 weeks		
Core Values	Maka-Diyos			Makatao			Makakalikasan		Makabansa		
General Idea	"My faith in God makes me..."			"My love for God helps me to be..."			"The love of God motivates to be..."		"God wants me to be..."		
EHSVEC Lessons	I Want to Love God Like Jesus	I Want to be Close to God Like Jesus		I Want to Love Others Like Jesus	I Want to Live Like Jesus	I Want to Give Like Jesus	I Want to Serve Like Jesus	I Want to Obey My Parents Like Jesus	I Want to be Helpful Like Jesus	I Want to Obey the Law Like Jesus	
PRIMARY 1-3	Self-confident <ul style="list-style-type: none"> God knows everything about you and He promised help me and not leave me – this is my confidence 	Prayerful and persevering <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I will not quit. Instead, I will pray about my situation. God will help me persevere through trials by giving me strength. 	Sincere and Grateful <ul style="list-style-type: none"> My faith in God must be sincere. My love for my fellowmen must also be sincere. Although I do not understand yet, I know that God knows what's best for me. 	Respectful <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I will respect my parents because God tells us to honor them. Loving others begin at home so I will be a loving child. 	Clean inside and out <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cleanliness is next to godliness. My body is the temple of God – I will take care of it. God is the God of order – so I will be orderly, as well. 	Generous <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I will show God that I love Him by loving others.. I can show this love by being generous. 	Compassionate to people indirectly <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I will take care of the environment because my actions – good or bad – will affect them. God told us to take care of the environment. 	Responsible and obedient <ul style="list-style-type: none"> When I am entrusted of something, I will not disappoint them. 	Helpful <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I will participate in community activities that help build the nation. 	A good citizen <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I will obey rules and regulations. I will not participate in acts of corruption. I will respecting my country and her symbols. 	
							Compassionate – to people directly <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To be truly generous, I need to feel how others feel. 				
INTERMEDIATE 4-6	Value and be confident of myself <ul style="list-style-type: none"> My worth is based on God's love for me. I know that God will help me achieve the things. 	Honest <ul style="list-style-type: none"> God is truth and He expects nothing less from me. I will not lie nor deceive others. 	Accountable and persevering <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I will take responsibility for my actions. If I make a mistake I will admit it and do better next time. Even if doing what is right is difficult sometimes, I will persevere. 	Patriotic by being respectful and patient. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> There will be times breaking the law is more convenient, such not using the overpass, I will be patient and use it. 	Clean inside and out <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I will keep my mind on things that are pure and will avoid saying or doing things that might offend others.. 	Good steward of people and the environment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> God wants me be a good steward of people. I will take care of those God has entrusted to my care. 	Good steward of people and the environment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I will take care of the environment because my actions – good or bad – will affect them. 	Patriotic and be good citizens <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To be a good citizen, I will be true to my pledge of allegiance. I will also promote my province to my friends. 	OBEDIENT AND HUMBLE I Am A Part Of The Whole. I Need Others And I Need Them, Too		
						THRIFTY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I can only give what I have, so I will spend my money wisely and save some in case others might need my help. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I admit that earth doesn't need to survive, but I cannot survive a single day without the oxygen that provides. 	In relation to my duty as a citizen, I will be...	COMPASSION of my neighbors	GRATEFUL to God of my country

EHSVEC CURRICULUM SPECIFICS

Comprehensive Approach to Students' Development Aligned with EHSVEC Curriculum Philosophy

HOLISTIC DEVELOPMENT

Aligned with our philosophy, we aim for Filipino youth of this generation and the generations to come to have the “abundant life” that our Lord Jesus came to provide. These curricular specifics aim to provide a comprehensive approach to students' development.

Our curriculum is designed to foster holistic development by addressing the cognitive, affective, and psycho-social aspects of education. This means that beyond academic excellence, we place significant emphasis on emotional intelligence, character building, and social responsibility. We believe that true education goes beyond the mere transfer of knowledge; it involves the formation of values and the nurturing of a compassionate, well-rounded individual who can contribute positively to society.

Cognitive Development	Affective Development	Psycho-Social Development	Spiritual Development	Preparing for Life's Challenges
<p>In line with the pursuit of abundant life, we ensure that our students gain a robust understanding of both spiritual and secular knowledge. This includes biblical principles to cultivate a worldview that recognizes the sovereignty of God in all aspects of life. Cognitive development is supported through a curriculum that encourages critical thinking, creativity, and intellectual curiosity.</p>	<p>The affective domain of our curriculum focuses on the emotional and moral growth of our students. By instilling Christian values and virtues, we aim to shape students' hearts and minds to reflect Christ-like character. Activities such as reflection journals, purpose statement assignments, and community service projects are integral components that help students internalize and live out the teachings of the Bible in their daily lives.</p>	<p>Recognizing that humans are inherently social beings, our curriculum includes components that promote healthy interpersonal relationships and social engagement. Group discussions, presentations, and collaborative projects are designed to enhance students' communication skills, teamwork, and empathy. Moreover, community service projects provide practical opportunities for students to apply their learning in real-world contexts, thereby fostering a sense of social responsibility and a heart for service.</p>	<p>At the heart of our philosophy is the belief that true fulfillment in life comes from a relationship with God. Our curriculum is therefore infused with opportunities for students to explore and deepen their faith. By fostering a strong spiritual foundation, we aim to guide students toward the abundant life that Jesus promised.</p>	<p>In equipping students for the challenges of life, we incorporate life skills education into our curriculum. This includes financial literacy, leadership training, and vocational guidance, ensuring that our students are well-prepared for future careers and life decisions. By addressing both practical and spiritual needs, we strive to produce graduates who are not only competent in their fields but also grounded in their faith and committed to living purposeful lives.</p>

GENERAL OBJECTIVE

To develop in students a deep understanding of their purpose in life and equip them with the knowledge, character, and skills to live a fulfilled and meaningful life in accordance with God's purpose, integrating their intellectual, emotional, and spiritual growth for holistic development.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

The Bible tells us "Jesus increased in wisdom and in stature, and in favor with God and man" (Luke 2:52). He increased physically, mentally, and emotionally, signifying human development. Hence, our specific objectives should also aim to target specific areas of development among our learners.

Cognitive Objectives

1. Analyze the relationship between purpose and fulfillment in life, identifying key biblical principles that guide one's understanding of life's true meaning (Ecclesiastes 12:1, John 17:3).
2. Identify the temporary nature of worldly pursuits and evaluate their role in shaping one's goals and aspirations (Isaiah 40:8, James 4:14).
3. Assess the role of education in personal development by linking academic learning with the discovery of one's purpose and fulfillment, integrating knowledge with wisdom and character (Proverbs 4:7).
4. Investigate philosophical and theological perspectives on human purpose to foster critical thinking about life's meaning from both a secular and Christian worldview (Pascal, 1670/1995).
5. Examine societal and cultural influences on individual purpose, comparing these to biblical teachings and personal experiences to cultivate a well-rounded perspective on identity and calling (Romans 12:2).

Affective Objectives

1. Foster a personal commitment to living a purpose-driven life, encouraging students to align their actions with a deeper understanding of God's plan for them (Matthew 22:37).
2. Promote a sense of personal fulfillment through spiritual growth, helping students experience joy and contentment as they grow in their relationship with God (John 10:10).
3. Cultivate empathy and compassion towards others, nurturing a mindset that seeks the welfare of others and promotes societal well-being in accordance with biblical teachings (Luke 10:27).
4. Encourage self-reflection on life choices and the impact of those choices on personal and spiritual growth, helping students make informed decisions that honor God (Proverbs 3:5-6).
5. Instill a sense of gratitude for life's purpose, helping students recognize the blessings that come with fulfilling their divine calling and appreciating the eternal perspective in daily living (1 Thessalonians 5:18).

Psycho-social Objectives

1. Develop resilience in the face of challenges, fostering a mindset that remains focused on the long-term goal of living a fulfilled and purposeful life despite external pressures (James 1:12).
2. Enhance interpersonal relationships by fostering understanding, communication, and collaboration, rooted in mutual respect and shared values of purpose and fulfillment (Philippians 2:4).

3. Encourage responsible decision-making that reflects the values of integrity, stewardship, and service to others, aligning personal choices with God’s will (Colossians 3:17).
4. Promote emotional intelligence and self-regulation, helping students manage their emotions and reactions in a way that supports their well-being and purpose-driven life (Galatians 5:22-23).
5. Build a supportive community where students can share their spiritual, academic, and emotional growth, and encourage one another in their pursuit of purpose and fulfillment (Hebrews 10:24-25).

COURSE REQUIREMENTS TO EVALUATE AND ASSESS STUDENTS

The assessment methods for this course will be to evaluate students holistically—cognitively, emotionally, and socially—while aligning with the course's overall objectives of discovering purpose and fulfillment in life.

The following requirements aim to measure students’ understanding, character development, and practical application of the lessons learned.

GRADING SCALE

- A (90-100%) - Excellent
- B (80-89%) - Good
- C (70-79%) - Satisfactory
- D (60-69%) - Needs Improvement
- F (Below 60%) - Fail

CATEGORY	AREA TO BE ASSESSED	OBJECTIVE	DESCRIPTION	EVALUATION CRITERIA	ASSESSMENT METHOD
Reflection Journal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cognitive • Affective 	To track personal growth and understanding of life’s purpose, fulfillment, and biblical teachings.	Students will keep a weekly journal, reflecting on the course's key lessons, personal insights, and how they are applying the principles of purpose, fulfillment, and happiness in their own lives. This journal will encourage deep introspection on spiritual, emotional, and cognitive growth.	Depth of reflection, critical thinking, evidence of personal growth, and alignment with course content (John 17:3; Proverbs 4:7).	Grading based on rubrics that evaluate clarity, insight, and consistency of thought.
Purpose Statement Assignment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cognitive 	To assess students' ability to articulate their understanding of life’s purpose in light of the course content.	Students will write a 3–5-page essay that articulates their understanding of their personal purpose in life, referencing both biblical and philosophical views. This assignment will encourage students to connect theory with personal experience, analyzing the relationship between knowledge and spiritual fulfillment.	Clear articulation of purpose, integration of course material, and application to personal life (Ecclesiastes 12:1; John 10:10).	Graded on clarity, coherence, and depth of understanding.
Group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Psycho-social 	To foster collaborative skills	Students will participate in small	Active participation,	Peer and instructor

Discussion and Presentation		and evaluate students' understanding of the course's key principles from different perspectives.	group discussions on a chosen topic related to purpose and fulfillment (e.g., "The Role of Society in Shaping Our Purpose," or "Balancing Worldly and Spiritual Pursuits"). Each group will prepare a presentation that synthesizes their findings and reflections.	ability to collaborate effectively, clear communication of ideas, and integration of biblical and philosophical perspectives (Philippians 2:4).	evaluation of participation, presentation quality, and depth of discussion.
Case Study Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cognitive • Affective 	To develop critical thinking and empathy by evaluating real-world scenarios related to purpose and fulfillment.	Students will analyze a real or hypothetical case study of a person struggling to find purpose and fulfillment in life (e.g., a character from literature or a historical figure). Students will assess the case based on the principles learned in the course and propose solutions grounded in biblical teachings.	Critical analysis, application of course content, and empathy for the individual's situation (Romans 12:2; Luke 10:27).	Written report and class discussion, graded based on the application of principles and solution viability.
Final Exam	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cognitive 	To assess students' comprehensive understanding of the course material.	A comprehensive written exam covering all course content, including biblical teachings, philosophical perspectives, and practical applications of purpose and fulfillment. The exam will consist of multiple-choice questions, short-answer questions, and an essay question.	Accuracy of responses, depth of understanding, and ability to apply course content in a practical context (Isaiah 40:8; James 4:14).	Graded based on correctness, clarity, and depth of analysis.
Community Service Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Psycho-social and Affective Evaluation 	To evaluate students' ability to apply the course's principles of purpose and fulfillment in a tangible way, contributing to their community.	Students will participate in a community service project where they can serve others while reflecting on their purpose and fulfillment. The project will require students to demonstrate leadership, empathy, and practical action in line with their values and the course content.	Initiative, impact on the community, and alignment with biblical principles of service (Matthew 22:39).	Project report and reflection paper, graded on the effectiveness and alignment with course objectives.

GRADING SYSTEM

The grading system for this course is designed to assess students holistically, measuring their cognitive understanding, emotional development, and social application of the principles of purpose and fulfillment in life. The grading categories align with the course objectives, ensuring a balanced evaluation of both theoretical knowledge and practical application.

Grading Category	Purpose	Assessment Criteria	Grading Breakdown
Reflection Journals – 20%	To track personal growth and understanding of the course material over time.	Depth of reflection, critical thinking, and connection to course content.	<p>A (90-100%): Deep personal reflection, clear understanding of course content, insightful connections.</p> <p>B (80-89%): Good reflection, clear understanding, some connection to course content.</p> <p>C (70-79%): Adequate reflection, limited understanding or weak connection to content.</p> <p>D (60-69%): Minimal reflection, lacks depth, minimal connection to course content.</p> <p>F (Below 60%): Lack of submission or reflection with no evident understanding.</p>
Purpose Statement Assignment – 25%	To evaluate students' ability to articulate their understanding of life's purpose and their personal reflections on it.	Clarity of purpose, integration of biblical principles, depth of reflection	<p>A (90-100%): Clear and well-organized, profound connection between personal purpose and biblical teachings.</p> <p>B (80-89%): Well-written, strong connection to course material, some depth.</p> <p>C (70-79%): Satisfactory articulation, limited integration of course content.</p> <p>D (60-69%): Weak articulation, unclear connection to purpose.</p> <p>F (Below 60%): Lack of submission or poor articulation.</p>
Group Discussion and Presentation – 15%	To evaluate teamwork, communication, and the ability to collaborate on a shared understanding of the course's principles.	Participation, contribution to the discussion, clarity of presentation, and the ability to integrate course material.	<p>A (90-100%): Active participation, strong presentation, effective teamwork.</p> <p>B (80-89%): Good participation, clear presentation, adequate teamwork.</p> <p>C (70-79%): Limited participation, presentation lacks clarity, minimal teamwork.</p> <p>D (60-69%): Poor participation, unclear presentation, ineffective teamwork.</p> <p>F (Below 60%): No participation or lack of presentation.</p>
Case Study Analysis – 15%	To assess the application of course principles in analyzing real-life scenarios.	Critical thinking, empathy, application of course concepts, solution quality.	<p>A (90-100%): Excellent analysis with insightful application and solutions grounded in course content.</p> <p>B (80-89%): Good analysis with clear application and solutions.</p> <p>C (70-79%): Basic analysis with minimal application and weak solutions.</p> <p>D (60-69%): Limited analysis, weak application of course content.</p>

			F (Below 60%): No submission or poor analysis.
Final Exam – 20%	To evaluate students' overall understanding of the course material.	Comprehensive knowledge of biblical, philosophical, and practical teachings on purpose and fulfillment.	<p>A (90-100%): Excellent understanding, clear, well-organized, insightful answers.</p> <p>B (80-89%): Good understanding, coherent answers, some depth.</p> <p>C (70-79%): Satisfactory understanding, answers are correct but lack depth.</p> <p>D (60-69%): Basic understanding, minimal answers with poor elaboration.</p> <p>F (Below 60%): Incomplete or incorrect answers.</p>
Community Service Project – 10%	To assess students' ability to translate the principles of purpose and fulfillment into social action.	Initiative, impact on the community, alignment with biblical principles of service.	<p>A (90-100%): Active leadership, impactful service, clear application of course principles.</p> <p>B (80-89%): Good participation, meaningful service, some application of principles.</p> <p>C (70-79%): Satisfactory participation, minimal impact, limited application of course content.</p> <p>D (60-69%): Limited participation or weak service impact.</p> <p>F (Below 60%): No participation or poorly executed project.</p>

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